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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY IN OUTDOOR PATIENTS**¹Dr. Saliha, ²Dr. Muhammad Irfan, ³Dr. Sharjeel Adnan¹Aziz Bhatti Shaheed Teaching Hospital Gujrat²Sheikh Zayed Medical College Rahimyar Khan³Sheikh Zayed Medical College Rahimyar Khan**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Humans get vitamin D from exposure to sunlight, from their diet, and from dietary supplements. A diet high in oily fish prevents vitamin D deficiency. Vitamin D deficiency is defined by most experts as a 25-hydroxyvitamin D level of less than 20 ng per milliliter (50 nmol per liter). This cross-sectional study was conducted in Sheikh Zayed Medical College Rahim Yar Khan. A total of 160 male and female patients presenting in outdoor department were included in this study. The mean age of the patients was 35.98±2.22 years. The mean vitamin D level among all the patients was 31.23±2.34 ng/mL. In this study, 39 (24.38%) patients were having vitamin D deficiency, 70 (43.75%) were having adequate levels and 51 (31.88%) had optimal levels of Vitamin D.

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INTRODUCTION:

Humans get vitamin D from exposure to sunlight, from their diet, and from dietary supplements. A diet high in oily fish prevents vitamin D deficiency. Solar ultraviolet B radiation (wavelength, 290 to 315 nm) penetrates the skin and converts 7-dehydrocholesterol to previtamin D₃, which is rapidly converted to vitamin D₃. Because any excess previtamin D₃ or vitamin D₃ is destroyed by sunlight, excessive exposure to sunlight does not cause vitamin D₃ intoxication (1-3).

Vitamin D deficiency is defined by most experts as a 25-hydroxyvitamin D level of less than 20 ng per milliliter (50 nmol per liter). 25-Hydroxyvitamin D levels are inversely associated with parathyroid hormone levels until the former reach 30 to 40 ng per milliliter (75 to 100 nmol per liter), at which point parathyroid hormone levels begin to level off (4-6).

Vitamin D is an important pro-hormone for optimal intestinal calcium absorption for mineralization of bone. Since the vitamin D receptor is present in multiple tissues, there has been interest in evaluating other potential functions of vitamin D, particularly in cardiovascular diseases. Vitamin D₂ and vitamin D₃ (D represents either D₂ or D₃) derived from supplements, fortified foods, and fish ingested from the diet are incorporated into chylomicrons and absorbed into the lymphatic system. From here they enter the circulation, where they are bound to the DBP and lipoproteins. Cross-sectional studies have reported that vitamin D deficiency is associated with

increased risk of cardiovascular disease, including hypertension, heart failure and ischemic heart disease (7-10).

This study was conducted in outdoor patients which present due to other condition i.e. diseases or pathologies. The purpose of this study is to find out the prevalence of Vitamin D deficiency in outdoor patients.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Sheikh Zayed Medical College Rahim Yar Khan. A total of 160 male and female patients presenting in outdoor department were included in this study. All the data was entered and analyzed in SPSS Ver. 25.0. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the patients was 35.98±2.22 years. Mean age of the male patients was 37.23±2.76 years and of female patients was 35.23±1.23 years. The mean vitamin D level among all the patients was 31.23±2.34 ng/mL. The mean vitamin D level among male patients was 32.34±3.33 ng/mL and among female patients was 29.34±1.23 ng/mL. In this study, 39 (24.38%) patients were having vitamin D deficiency, 70 (43.75%) were having adequate levels and 51 (31.88%) had optimal levels of Vitamin D. Distribution of patients according to condition presentation is given in graph:

DISCUSSION:

Vitamin D deficiency is now recognized as a pandemic. The major cause of vitamin D deficiency is the lack of appreciation that sun exposure in moderation is the major source of vitamin D for most humans. Very few foods naturally contain vitamin D, and foods that are fortified with vitamin D are often inadequate to satisfy either a child's or an adult's vitamin D requirement. Vitamin D deficiency causes rickets in children and will precipitate and exacerbate osteopenia, osteoporosis, and fractures in adults. Vitamin D deficiency has been associated with increased risk of common cancers, autoimmune diseases, hypertension, and infectious diseases (1, 5, 9). A circulating level of 25-hydroxyvitamin D of >75 nmol/L, or 30 ng/mL, is required to maximize vitamin D's beneficial effects for health. In the absence of adequate sun exposure, at least 800–1000 IU vitamin D3/d may be needed to achieve this in children and adults. Vitamin D2 may be equally effective for maintaining circulating concentrations of 25-hydroxyvitamin D when given in physiologic concentrations (2, 4, 10).

Without vitamin D, only 10 to 15% of dietary calcium and about 60% of phosphorus is absorbed. The interaction of 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D with the vitamin D receptor increases the efficiency of intestinal calcium absorption to 30 to 40% and phosphorus absorption to approximately 80%. Vitamin D deficiency causes global poor mineralization of the skeleton. Clinical and radiological bone manifestations predominate in areas of rapid bone growth, including the long bone epiphyses and the costochondral junctions. This is why rickets is mostly observed before 18 months of age, with maximum frequency between the ages of 4 and 12 months. Skeletal deformities are usually a result of long-standing rickets. Hypertrophy of the costochondral junctions leads to beading and the classic rachitic rosary that progresses with involution of the ribs and protrusion of the sternum (pigeon chest) and recession of the costochondral junctions and transverse depressions causing Harrison's groove (3, 7, 8).

CONCLUSION:

In patients presenting in outdoor department, mostly have adequate levels of Vitamin D. In patients having lower levels of Vitamin D, supplementation should be properly done.

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